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SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D8.5- FINAL REPORT ON DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES.
FINAL REPORT ON THE PERFORMED ACTIONS AND EFFICIENCY OF THE
DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES ACTIONS AND EFFICIENCY
OF THE DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

Universidade de Vigo

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Summary

This document constitutes Deliverable D8.5 – the **Final Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities**. It provides a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination actions implemented throughout the duration of the project, assessing both their execution and overall effectiveness.

The report builds upon the foundations laid out in **Deliverable D8.1 – Plan of Communication**, submitted in **Month 6**, which defined the goals, strategies, guidelines, and workflows for all partners involved in communication activities. It also follows up on **Deliverable D8.4**, submitted in **Month 30**, which served as a mid-term evaluation of the efficiency of these activities and proposed adjustments for improvement.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
D8.5	WP8_Communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholders engagement
Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(s)
FEUGA	Tamara Rodríguez [FEUGA]
Versions (updates)	Date
V1	28.05.2025
Deliverable Quality Check	Date
David Fernández Calviño [UVIGO]	29.05.2025

Planned Delivery Date		Final Delivery Date	
31.05.2025		29.05.2025	
Type of deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	x
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethycs	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	x
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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1 Introduction

This document constitutes **Deliverable D8.5 – Final Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities** of the SoildiverAgro project. It presents a comprehensive summary of the **communication and dissemination efforts** carried out throughout the project's lifetime, with a focus on evaluating their **implementation, reach, and overall effectiveness** in supporting the project's objectives.

The report builds upon the framework established in **Deliverable D8.1 – Communication and Dissemination Plan**, submitted in **Month 6**, which defined the key goals, target audiences, messaging strategies, tools, and workflows to be followed by all consortium partners. Additionally, it draws on the insights and evaluations presented in **Deliverable D8.4**, submitted in **Month 30**, which served as a **mid-term review** of the communication strategy, identifying strengths, challenges, and recommendations for improvement.

Together, these deliverables form the backbone of the project's communication strategy, ensuring a **coherent, multi-actor, and impact-driven approach**. This final report reflects on the outcomes achieved, lessons learned, and the legacy of SoildiverAgro's dissemination efforts as the project concludes.

2 Key Communication Highlights – Final SoildiverAgro Report

An overview of visitors, followers, and other communication materials is presented in the graph below, highlighting the key figures at a glance.

Figure 1 SoildiverAgro Communication Highlights

3 Objectives and targets

The main objectives outlined in the **Communication Plan (Deliverable D8.1)** were as follows:

1. **To raise awareness and interest** among various actors and end-users involved in or impacted by the project.
2. **To identify, engage, and mobilize stakeholders** through a multi-actor approach, ensuring broad and inclusive participation.
3. **To facilitate knowledge transfer** by producing communication and dissemination materials, and through active participation in social media, conferences, events, and networking activities. Collaboration with other relevant projects and initiatives, such as EIP-Agri, was also emphasized as a key element.
4. **To ensure a multiplier effect** by reaching wider audiences through targeted activities, including Communities of Practice, end-user workshops, discussion groups under WP2, field days, and guided visits for students.

The target audiences for these activities were also defined in Deliverable D8.1.

Table 1 Target audiences for communication activities

TARGET AUDIENCES FOR COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	
Level	Target group
Scientific Community (SC)	Research centres, universities, technological centres
Policy (PO)	Policy-makers, regulators, European associations, networks and institutions (CEMR, CEMA, EEA, EDNCP, RISE, ELO, BEUC, COPA-COGECA), NGOs (CONCORD, WWF, EEB, EFNCP, IFOAM,), international bodies (UNCBD, UNFCCC, UNCCD)
Public administrations (PA)	Local, regional and national public administrations of each country
Direct end users (EUS)	Farmers, farmer associations, agricultural and environmental technicians, agribusiness, agroindustry, agricultural consultants, farming supplier companies, service providers
EIP-AGRI (EIP)	EIP-AGRI (EIP) Focus Groups and Operational Groups
Civil society (CS)	Local/ regional consumer associations, educators, students

Next table shows the key messages to address target audiences:

Table 2 Key messages

KEY MESSAGES		
- Agricultural sustainability	- Soil quality	- Reduction of GHG
- Soil biodiversity	- Carbon sequestering	- Costs Reduction

- Low-input management processes	- Innovative cropping systems	- Climate change management
- Increasing land productivity	- Saving energy	- Economic benefits
- Reducing environmental impact	- Plant growth promoting products	- Circular Economy
- Best management practices	- Accessing new markets	- Farm profitability
- Reducing economic risks	- Sustainable production	- Rural growth
- Rural Policies	- Products for responsible markets	- Bioeconomy

Each target group has different interests and expectations. We mix both variables in the next table and define what key messages are important by target group.

Table 3 Key messages by target group

TARGET GROUP	KEY MESSAGES
Direct end users (EUS)	• Increasing land productivity
	• Best management practices
	• Reducing economic risks
	• Innovative cropping systems
	• Saving energy
	• Plant growth promoting products
	• Accessing new markets
	• Costs Reduction
	• Economic benefits
	• Farm profitability
Public administrations (PA)	• Agricultural Sustainability
	• Soil biodiversity
	• Reducing environmental impact
	• Reducing economic risks
	• Rural Policies
	• Saving energy
	• Sustainable production
	• Circular Economy
	• Rural growth
	• Bioeconomy
Scientific community (SC)	• Soil biodiversity
	• Low-input management processes
	• Soil quality
	• Carbon sequestering
	• Reduction of GHG
	• Climate change management
• Circular Economy	

TARGET GROUP	KEY MESSAGES
Policy (PO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural growth • Increasing land productivity • Saving energy • Agricultural Sustainability • Reducing economic risks • Reducing environmental impact • Rural Policies • Sustainable production • Circular Economy • Rural growth • Bioeconomy • Climate change management • Products for responsible markets
EIP-AGRI (EIP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing land • Innovative cropping systems • Farm profitability • Best management practices • Products for responsible markets • Soil biodiversity • Rural growth • Agricultural Sustainability • Rural Policies • Rural growth
General Public (GP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural Sustainability • Soil biodiversity • Reducing environmental impact • Sustainable production • Climate change management • Products for responsible markets

4 Communications, channels and tools

For the **SoildiverAgro** project to achieve meaningful impact, the communication, dissemination, and exploitation of its objectives must be strategically planned and implemented in a creative, original, and innovative way. Effective communication plays a central role in ensuring the project's visibility, reaching its target audiences, and fostering lasting engagement.

To support this goal, SoildiverAgro has developed a variety of communication channels and tools designed to engage stakeholders and encourage interaction with the project and its partners. These include both online and offline platforms, as well as a comprehensive set of resources—such as templates, branding guidelines, and online materials—made available to all Consortium members. These tools help ensure consistency and support partners in producing high-quality communication outputs.

This section provides an overview of the main communication channels employed by the project and the tools created to facilitate dissemination activities. As the project progresses, these channels and tools were regularly reviewed and updated to reflect evolving communication needs and project developments.

4.1 Engaging channels

4.1.1 Website

SoildiverAgro's website (<http://www.soildiveragro.eu>) is the main online communication channel of the project. In order to increase the project's visibility, all partners included a link to the SoildiverAgro website from their own website, and share it through their social media accounts, if possible.

Contents are written in clear and accessible language in order to reach as many people as possible.

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Figure 2 SoildiverAgro website

Due to challenges with the original website designer, FEUGA assumed responsibility for two key activities in recent months: updating the translated content across the site and conducting a comprehensive review of the website's overall performance. Once these tasks were completed, FEUGA continued to actively update and enrich the website with new project results, news, and activities to ensure the platform remains current and informative.

News published

142 posts have been published since website launch, all of them are categorized so we can easily filter news related to type of crop, region involved... We also included tags on each so it increases the website SEO for online searchers as google.

Figure 3 SoildiverAgro website news

<input type="checkbox"/> Title		Author	Categories	Tags	Date
<input type="checkbox"/> SoildiverAgro Final Event: results, collaboration, and future perspectives	+ + + + + + + + + +	Tamara Rodríguez	Event, General	Final event, May 2025, ourense	Published 2025/05/20 at 11:03 am
<input type="checkbox"/> SoildiverAgro hosts its Final Event Next Week	+ + + + + + + + + +	Tamara Rodríguez	Event, General	Final event, May 2025, Mosteiro de Santo Estevo, ourense	Published 2025/05/07 at 1:53 pm
<input type="checkbox"/> SoildiverAgro and AGROSUS Join Forces for a Field Day in the Lusitanian Region	+ + + + + + + + + +	Tamara Rodríguez	Event, lusitanian	AGROSUS, joint event, Limia, Result presentations, soildiveragro	Published 2025/05/05 at 1:06 pm
<input type="checkbox"/> SoildiverAgro Survey Now Open: Share Your Feedback on Policy Recommendations and the Project Impact Edit Quick Edit View	+ + + + + + + + + +	Tamara Rodríguez	General, New	eusurvey, policy recommendations, survey	Published 2025/04/30 at 2:13 pm
<input type="checkbox"/> SoildiverAgro Joins the SOILGUARD Event: "From Soil Science to Policy" at the Forum for the Future of Agriculture	+ + + + + + + + + +	Tamara Rodríguez	Event, General	brussels, event, Forum for Future Agriculture, Soilguard	Published 2025/03/26 at 1:27 pm

Figure 4 SoildiverAgro website news list

To improve navigation and regional relevance, specific categories were created on the website, allowing news items to be directly linked to each regional community. As shown in the image below, when accessing the "Stakeholder Community" section and selecting a region, users can view all news related to that area. This functionality is made possible through the strategic categorization of published content.

Krista Peltoniemi

Doctor (PhD) Krista Peltoniemi is a senior scientist and has expertise in soil microbiomes. She has experience in studies of soil microbial communities (fungi, bacteria, actinobacteria, methanogenic archaea and methanotrophic bacteria), their diversity after environmental changes and their relationships in various environments. Her main task in the projects is to act as a regional coordinator for Boreal region on behalf of all Finnish partners Luke, Petla, Kilpiä and Tyynelä farms. She is involved in all WPs, and her expertise will be utilized in the soil microbiological analysis concerning WP3 and WP5. Regional coordinator of boreal region, deputy coordinator of WP3.

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Check the Boreal section at [Regional Communities](#) and [case studies booklet](#) here.

News about the Boreal area

New video from Boreal region taking gas samples (CS14)

www.soildiveragro.eu

Figure 5 SoildiverAgro related news with regional communities

Additionally, to compile all publications and dissemination materials, a dedicated webpage titled "[Toolbox Kit](#)" was created. This platform provides a **centralized and accessible**

repository for all project-related resources, ensuring easy access for stakeholders and the general public.

Figure 6 Toolbox Kit webpage

Website metrics

As of the end of May 2025, at the time of this report's preparation, the SoildiverAgro website had registered a total of 24,470 visits from 22,710 unique users, who collectively accessed a total of 835 published pages.

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WEBSITE LOCATION TRAFFIC

Jun 1, 2019 - May 25, 2025

Analytics Real time

Website

soildiveragro.eu

Figure 7 SoildiverAgro Website metrics

4.1.2 Social networks

Social Media Professional social media accounts for SoildiverAgro were created (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Youtube). It was expected at least 1000 followers in each social network account created. The following analysis is recorded since the beginning of the project until the end of May 2025.

- Facebook

Figure 8 SoildiverAgro Facebook page

Facebook activity over the six-year duration of the SoildiverAgro project shows a total of 173 followers, more than 2,000 page visits, and over 280 posts published. These figures reflect consistent engagement and content dissemination through the platform.

Figure 9 SoildiverAgro Facebook overview

SoildiverAgro reached an engagement of 10.68 with a total of 5624 interactions and 56.12K impressions achieved over the duration of the project.

Figure 10 SoildiverAgro Facebook Engagement

- **Facebook group**

Creation of a **Facebook group** for the **SDA Community** so that there is continuous communication, interaction and exchange. *Regional Coordinators and Communication Coordinator will manage the group, in English.*

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Figure 11 SoildiverAgro Community Facebook Group

- X (before Twitter)

Figure 12 SoildiverAgro Twitter Account

Created in November 2019 SoildiverAgro twitter account counts with **1104 followers** and **follows 1332 external accounts** related to the project. **460 posts** were created on this account showing project progress, interesting events, publications...

Figure 13 SoildiverAgro Twitter Community

Over the six-year duration of the project, the SoildiverAgro Twitter account achieved a 5.19 of engagement with a total of 51.89K impressions.

Figure 14 SoildiverAgro Twitter Engagement

Most of the content was original, but also other interesting accounts were retweeted when content was related to the project.

Figure 15 SoildiverAgro Twitter content

- **LinkedIn**

Figure 16 SoildiverAgro LinkedIn account

SoildiverAgro have 366 followers at linkedin with 24 new ones from last month analysis.

Figure 17 SoildiverAgro LinkedIn followers

Regarding the characteristics of SoildiverAgro's LinkedIn followers, the majority are based in Belgium and in various regions of Spain, particularly in the cities of Vigo and Santiago.

Figure 18 SoildiverAgro LinkedIn followers profile

In terms of professional occupation, 18.9% are engaged in research activities, while 10.4% are involved in business development. Other notable areas of expertise among our followers include project management, education, and engineering.

Figure 19 SoildiverAgro LinkedIn followers job position

SoildiverAgro LinkedIn profile has reached an engagement of 12.97, achieving a total of 3903 interactions and 30.09K impressions.

Figure 20: SoildiverAgro LinkedIn engagement

- Youtube

Since its launch in December 2019, the **SoildiverAgro YouTube channel** has attracted **30 subscribers** and accumulated **3495 views**, and **49 videos produced**. The channel serves as a

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visual communication tool, supporting the dissemination of project activities, case study updates, and event highlights to a broader audience.

Figure 21 SoildiverAgro Youtube account

Figure 22 SoildiverAgro Youtube traffic

An analysis of the SoildiverAgro YouTube channel traffic reveals the primary ways users access its video content. A significant portion of views—**54,3%** originates from **YouTube’s suggested videos**, indicating that the platform’s algorithm has effectively recommended the content to relevant audiences. Additionally, **15,6%** of views come from **external sources**, such as embedded links on websites, social media posts, or newsletters. Finally, **10,2%** of views are categorized as **direct traffic or from unknown sources**, which may include users who accessed the videos via bookmarks, direct URL entry, or untracked platforms.

This distribution highlights the importance of optimizing content for discoverability on YouTube and ensuring strong integration with external communication channels.

Figure 23 SoildiverAgro Youtube traffic

The **most viewed videos** to date include:

- *Lusitanean región sowing wheat*
- *SoildiverAgro Project Officer Christopher*
- *Soildiveragro Official video*

These videos have helped raise awareness of the project's goals and results, providing accessible, multimedia content for stakeholders, practitioners, and the general public.

Figure 24 SoildiverAgro Youtube content

4.1.3 Newsletters

SoildiverAgro uses the Mailchimp platform to create and distribute its newsletters. These newsletters are integrated into the project website under the [Newsletters section](#) and are also sent by email to subscribers who have joined through the website's subscription form.

The SoildiverAgro newsletter has served as a key communication tool throughout the project, providing updates on research progress, events, publications, and stakeholder engagement activities. Its performance was tracked using standard email marketing metrics, offering valuable insights into its reach and effectiveness:

- **Open Rate:** This indicates the percentage of recipients who opened the newsletter.
- **Click Rate:** The click rate shows the percentage of readers who clicked on one or more links within the email. This metric highlights engagement and interest in accessing additional resources such as articles, videos, or reports.
- **Total Deliveries:** A total of 6 newsletters were successfully delivered to subscribers, ensuring consistent dissemination to a wide audience.

These figures demonstrate that the newsletter effectively reached and engaged its target audiences, supporting the project's broader dissemination and communication objectives.

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Figure 25 SoildiverAgro Newsletter section

Each newsletter edition includes key sections such as upcoming events, featured articles, project deliverables, and important updates, highlighting the most relevant news from recent months.

As of the date of this report, **six newsletters** have been published. The first edition was released in **July 2020**, followed by one each year, with the most recent issue published in **May 2025**.

Below, you can find an **image of each edition**, along with a **link to access them** and a brief **report on the impact achieved**, including key performance indicators such as number of views, open rates, and click-through rates where available.

First newsletter: [Newsletter n° 1 / July 2020](#)

The screenshot shows the layout of the first newsletter. At the top, there is a header with the text "View this email in your browser" and "Newsletter n° 1 / July 2020". Below this is a large image of a field with the word "NEWSLETTER" overlaid. The main content is organized into several sections:

- Consultations with stakeholders Finland and Spain start the debates:** This section includes a photo of hands being joined together and text stating that on the 5th (Finland) and 11th (Spain) of March, SOILDIVERAGRO started debates with farmers to implement more sustainable agricultural management practices. A "Read more" link is provided.
- Two success discussion groups in Belgium:** This section describes two virtual discussion groups organized in Belgium. The first took place on May 19th, focusing on vegetable production. The second took place on June 30th, focusing on arable farming. Both sessions involved fifteen participants with diverse backgrounds. A "Read more" link is provided.
- Visit our website:** This section features a screenshot of the SoildiverAgro website, showing a "Learn more" button and social media icons.
- First SoildiverAgro regional meeting in Germany:** This section includes a photo of a group of people and text stating that SOILDIVERAGRO aims to organize 5 regional meetings. The first meeting took place in Germany on February 19th. A "Read more" link is provided.
- Finland hosts the first field visits:** This section includes two photos of field visits. The text describes the first field days held in July, attended by about 75 farmers and advisors. Participants performed soil tests and a simplified soil diagnosis. A "Read more" link is provided.

At the bottom of the newsletter, there is a footer with the text "Copyright © 2020 SoildiverAgro. All rights reserved." and a "mailchimp" logo.

Figure 26 SoildiverAgro First Newsletter

First newsletter was sent to 9 recipients and opened by 4 of them.

Newsletter N° 1 / July 2020

Switch report ▾

Overview Activity ▾ Click Performance Content Optimizer Social E-commerce Inbox Analytics360

9 Recipients

Audience: SoildiverAgro

Delivered: Fri, Jul 24, 2020 3:18 am

Subject: Newsletter n° 1 / July 2020

[View email](#) · [Download](#) · [Print](#) · [Share](#)

4 Opened	0 Clicked	0 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
-------------	--------------	--------------	-------------------

Figure 27 SoildiverAgro first newsletter campaign

Second newsletter: [Newsletter n° 2 / June 2021](#)

Figure 28 SoildiverAgro second newsletter

Second newsletter was sent to 19 recipients, 9 opened it and 4 clicked on some content. It was open 47 times, has 19 clicks and last click was on 9/23/21.

Figure 29 SoildiverAgro second newsletter campaign

Third newsletter: [Newsletter n° 3 / May 2022](#)

The third SoildiverAgro newsletter (Newsletter N° 3, May 2022) was distributed in May 2022. Out of the 23 recipients, the newsletter was opened by 12 users, indicating a 30% engagement rate for this communication.

Figure 30 SoildiverAgro third newsletter

Figure 31 SoildiverAgro third newsletter campaign

Figure 32 SoildiverAgro third newsletter results

Forth newsletter [Newsletter n° 4/ June 2023](#)

Figure 33 SoildiverAgro fourth newsletter

Unfortunately, due to an error during distribution, this newsletter was sent to only one recipient. As a result, the analytical data is not valid and cannot be considered representative.

Newsletter n° 4/June 2023 View email	Recipients	1
	Audience	SoildiverAgro
	Subject	Newsletter n° 4/June 2023
	Status	Sent Wed June 12, 2024 8:19 am
	Segment: Targeted Contacts	

Figure 34 SoildiverAgro fourth newsletter campaign

Fifth newsletter: [Newsletter n° 5/December 2024](#)

The fifth SoildiverAgro newsletter was sent on December 17th, 2024, and was opened by 46 out of 73 recipients, demonstrating a significant increase in engagement compared to previous editions.

Figure 35 SoildiverAgro fifth newsletter

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Figure 36 SoildiverAgro fourth newsletter campaign

Sixth newsletter: [Newsletter n°6 / May 2025](#)

The last newsletter was sent on May 28th gathering all the results achieved and latest news and publication of this final phase of the project. As the newsletter was only recently sent, analytics are not yet available at the time of this report.

SoildiverAgro final event

SoildiverAgro hosted its final event at the **Parador de Santo Estevo Ribas de Sil (Ourense, Galicia)** on **May 13-15th**. Over these three days, participants presented key results from across the case studies, took part in field visits, and engaged in discussions on the project's legacy. A highlight of the event was a knowledge transfer session with other European soil biodiversity projects, where challenges, insights, and future collaboration opportunities were shared. The event marked an important milestone in closing the project while looking ahead to its long-term impact.

[Read more](#)

Figure 37 SoildiverAgro sixth newsletter

4.1.4 Photos, videos, infographics and animations

Galleries of images were uploaded by case study to the Gallery section of the website and infographics were created by case study for the [Regional communities and Case study booklet](#) recently published.

Figure 38 SoildiverAgro case studies infographics

Also several animations were created and shared on the project’s social media channels and website to mark special events and occasions. These included animated Christmas cards, announcements for project meetings, and other promotional materials designed to engage the audience and raise visibility around key moments throughout the project.

SoildiverAgro General Assembly Cartagena June 22

Partners meeting to explore first results and project future activities

Happy World Soil Day!

New community launched at SoildiverAgro project

Figure 39 SoildiverAgro animations

Figure 40 SoildiverAgro social media christmas card

Figure 41 SoildiverAgro social media animation

Additionally, some video series were produced to promote the work of SoildiverAgro and introduce the people behind it. These included a series of interviews with the regional coordinators, the official SoildiverAgro animated video which was translated into six different languages, and a collection of videos showcasing the agricultural practices implemented in each case study. Toward the end of the project, a final video series was developed to highlight the best management practices identified in each region.

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	Best Management Practices – Atlantic Central Region SoildiverAgro C... In this short video, we present the best management practices from the Atlantic Central Region, implemented in Case Study 8 of the SoildiverAgro...
	Best Management Practices – Atlantic Central Region SoildiverAgro C... In this video, we present the best management practices from the Atlantic Central Region, implemented in Case Study 8 of the SoildiverAgro project:...
	Best Management Practices - Nemoral Region SoildiverAgro Case Stu... In this short video, we showcase the best soil management practices developed in the Nemoral Region as part of the SoildiverAgro project,...
	Best Management Practices - Nemoral Region SoildiverAgro Case Stu... In this video, we showcase the best soil management practices developed in the Nemoral Region as part of the SoildiverAgro project, featured in Case...
	Best Management Practices - Boreal Region SoildiverAgro Case Study ... In this video, we present he best management practices from the Boreal Region, developed as part of the SoildiverAgro project through Case Studies...
	Best Management Practices - Boreal Region SoildiverAgro Case Study ... In this video, we present he best management practices from the Boreal Region, developed as part of the SoildiverAgro project through Case Studies...
	Best Management Practices – Lusitanian Region SoildiverAgro Case ... In this short video, we showcase the best management practice from the Lusitanian Region, implemented in Case Study 3 *Suitable crop...

Figure 42 SoildiverAgro best management practices video series

	SoildiverAgro Continental Region Coordinator Stefan Schrader In this interview, Stefan Schrader from Thünen-Institute of Biodiversity (Continetal Region) introduces himself and explains his role in the...
	SoildiverAgro Boreal Region Coordinator Krista Peltoniemi In this interview, Krista Peltoniemi from LUKE (Boreal Region) introduces herself and explains his role in the SoildiverAgro project and what farmers...
	SoildiverAgro Nemoral Region Coordinator Merrit Shanskiy In this interview, Merrit Shanskiy from EULS (Nemoral Region) introduces herself and explains his role in the SoildiverAgro project and what farmers...
	SoildiverAgro Atlantic Central Region Coordinator Lieven Waeyenberge In this interview, Lieven Waeyenberge from ILVO (Atlantic Central Region) introduces himself and explains his role in the SoildiverAgro project and wh...
	SoildiverAgro Lusitanian Regional Coordinator David Fernández In this interview, David Fernández from @UVigo (Project coordinator and head of the Lusitanian Region) introduces himself and explains his role in...

Figure 43 Regional coordinators interview series

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

	<p>SoildiverAgro Official video subtitles in Dutch</p> <p>De bodembiodiversiteit in Europese agro-ecosystemen herstellen of verrijken om hun stabiliteit en veerkracht te bevorderen, externe inputs te verminderen...</p>
	<p>Official Soildiveragro video in German</p> <p>Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance...</p>
	<p>Official Soildiveragro video in Czech</p> <p>Zvyšování biologické rozmanitosti půdy v evropských agroekosystémech za účelem podpory jejich stability a odolnosti snížením vnějších vstupů a...</p>
	<p>Video oficial SoildiverAgro H2020 (GL)</p> <p>Mellora da biodiversidade do solo nos agroecosistemas europeos para promover a súa estabilidade e resistencia reducindo os insumos externos e...</p>
	<p>Soildiveragro official video Finnish</p> <p>Eurooppalaisten agroekosysteemien maaperän biologisen monimuotoisuuden parantaminen sekä niiden vakauden ja kestävyys...</p>

Figure 44 Official animated video

	<p>Lusitanian region sowing wheat (3)</p> <p>Añadir descripción</p>
	<p>Lusitanian region sowing wheat (2)</p> <p>Añadir descripción</p>
	<p>Lusitanian region sowing wheat (1)</p> <p>From A Limia, Sandiás municipality for Case study 3 and 5</p>

Figure 45 Case study video series

4.1.5 Consortium tools including guidelines and templates

As part of **Deliverable D8.1 – Communication and Dissemination Plan**, a **social media toolkit** was provided, accompanied by a **style guide** and a set of **templates**. These resources were designed to support partners in both internal and external communications related to the SoildiverAgro project, ensuring consistency and alignment across all dissemination activities.

- Cartel A3
- Poster A0
- Brochure
- Practice Abstracts
- Roll-up
- Template ppt
- Template deliverable

- Template agenda
- Template list of participants
- Template Events
- Template News
- Template information sheet
- Template consent
- Template letter of invitation
- Social media guidelines

Additional materials were developed and added later on, based on the evolving needs and requests of project partners, further strengthening communication efforts throughout the project's lifetime.

- COP partners guide

Figure 46 SoildiverAgro partners guide for community creation

- Regional Communities and Case Studies Booklet

Throughout the project, SoildiverAgro produced six editions of the *Regional Communities and Case Studies Booklet*. Each edition presented updates on the progress, insights, and findings from the regional case studies across the participating countries. These booklets served as a key communication tool to share localized outcomes with stakeholders.

Figure 47 SoildiverAgro Regional communities and Case studies Booklet

All of these templates were also placed at the DPV Collaborative platform where project share all documents between partners.

4.1.6 Communication campaigns

4 campaigns were performed during the project lifetime to promote SoildiverAgro's activities, engage stakeholders, and increase the visibility and impact of the project.

The first one, was launched at the beginning of the project for KOM public event serving as an initial introduction to the project's objectives and partners.

The second campaign accompanied the launch of the Stakeholder Community, including press releases, social media posts, website updates, pop-ups, and the design of promotional banners to encourage participation and engagement.

The third campaign supported SoildiverAgro's involvement in *Suelos Vivos: European Innovation to Transform Galicia*, a joint event held to celebrate World Soil Day. This special regional event featured discussion panels and a networking fair, with SoildiverAgro participating alongside other European projects such as AGROSUS, MRV4SOC, MAR2PROTECT, Alert-PFAS, FIREPOCTEP+, DRYAD, and SUS-SOIL. The project also led a dedicated workshop on strategic management for stakeholder engagement. This campaign included a press release, as well as visual materials such as banners and creative content for social media and the project website.

Finally, the fourth and final campaign was launched at the conclusion of the project to disseminate final results and maximize the visibility and legacy of SoildiverAgro. This included a comprehensive press release distributed to local, national, and European media outlets,

highlighting the project's key outcomes and long-term contributions to sustainable agriculture and soil biodiversity.

Pop-up at website

Figure 48 SoildiverAgro website pop-up

Banners were created in different languages and are included in regional pages' description linked to the form related to the region.

Figure 49 SoildiverAgro campaign banners

Forms were created at regional languages and linked to each banner for engaging regional stakeholders.

Figure 50 SoildiverAgro campaign forms

Press release

Figure 51 SoildiverAgro campaign press release

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

Los asistentes podrán descubrir cómo los resultados de estos proyectos pueden beneficiar directamente a Galicia, contribuyendo a una gestión más sostenible de los suelos agrícolas y forestales, la biodiversidad y la adaptación al cambio climático en nuestra región.

La jornada cerrará con la **Soil Hub Fair**, una oportunidad excepcional centrada en fomentar el networking y la colaboración, reuniendo una gran variedad de proyectos e iniciativas relacionadas con la salud del suelo y la sostenibilidad. Los participantes podrán interactuar con expertos a través de **sesiones de pósteres, stands, presentaciones flash talks y talleres prácticos**.

Este formato interactivo está diseñado para fomentar el intercambio de ideas, promover el uso de buenas prácticas y alentar nuevas colaboraciones. Soil Hub Fair es la iniciativa perfecta para quien tenga una idea de proyecto, quiera presentar sus resultados, conocer casos de éxito o establecer nuevas conexiones.

Además del espacio de networking, contaremos con un taller del proyecto europeo **SoildiverAgro** centrado en fomentar las **Estrategias de facilitación para gestionar grupos de actores clave** en proyectos europeos. La jornada incluye los **eventos de lanzamiento de 6 proyectos de innovación de grupos operativos supra-autonómicos** de la AEI-Agri (convocatoria 2023), que tendrán lugar en dos sesiones paralelas:

Figure 52 SoildiverAgro Suelos Vivos press release

Figure 53 SoildiverAgro final results press release

Social networks post

Figure 54 SoildiverAgro campaign posts

Figure 55 SoildiverAgro Suelos Vivos promotion

Video

As the campaign was launched at the World Soil day we created a video joining both issues.

Figure 56 SoildiverAgro campaign video

4.2 Publications

Over the course of the project, SoildiverAgro produced a total of 20 scientific articles, 3 data sets, 20 posters, 1 booklet, 5 books, 114 Practice Abstracts and 6 Policy Briefs. These outputs reflect the scientific and technical advancements achieved and contribute to the dissemination of project results to both academic and professional audiences. Additionally, a **Decision Support Tool (DST)** and a **Survey on Policy Recommendations** were developed to help end users make informed decisions based on the project results and to better understand the **perceptions, needs, and priorities of stakeholders** regarding soil biodiversity and sustainable agricultural practices.

All publications are available through the project website at the [“Toolbox Kit” section](#), and have been promoted via newsletters, press releases, and social media channels to ensure broad visibility. Additionally, all materials have been uploaded to the Zenodo open-access repository, accessible at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/soildiveragro-h2020>, in alignment with the project's commitment to open science and knowledge sharing.

4.2.1 Scientific Articles

As part of the **SoildiverAgro** project, a total of **20 scientific articles** have been published in peer-reviewed journals and specialized magazines. These publications cover a range of topics related to **soil biodiversity, agroecological practices and environmental impact**, contributing valuable knowledge to the scientific community and supporting evidence-based decision-making in sustainable agriculture.

All scientific articles are accessible through the "**Toolbox Kit**" section of the SoildiverAgro website.

Table 4 Scientific articles

PUBLICATIONS			
Type	Title	Link	Zenodo
Article	Manure management and soil biodiversity Towards more sustainable food systems in the EU	Manure management and soil biodiversity Towards more sustainable food systems in the EU Zenodo	Yes
Article	Temporal and Cultivar-Specific Effects on Potato Root and Soil Fungal Diversity	Temporal and Cultivar-Specific Effects on Potato Root and Soil Fungal Diversity Zenodo	yes
Article	SoildiverAgro: stabiele en weerbare landbouwsystemen door verrijkt bodemleven	https://www.nobl.be/sites/default/files/files/nobl%20NL%202020%20webversie.pdf	No
Article	Soil and climatic characteristics and farming system shape fungal communities in European wheat fields	Soil and climatic characteristics and farming system shape fungal communities in European wheat fields	yes
Article	Opportunity of the NEGFY Decision Support System for the Sustainable Control of Potato Late Blight in A Limia (NW of Spain)	Opportunity of the NEGFY Decision Support System for the Sustainable Control of Potato Late Blight in A Limia (NW of Spain)	Yes
Article	Assessing the diversity of nematodes in the Store Mosse National Park (Sweden) using metabarcoding	Assessing the diversity of nematodes in the Store Mosse National Park (Sweden) using metabarcoding	No
Article	Effect of Biofertilizers on Broccoli Yield and Soil Quality Indicators	Effect of Biofertilizers on Broccoli Yield and Soil Quality Indicators	yes

PUBLICATIONS

Article	Do contaminants compromise the use of recycled nutrients in organic agriculture? A review and synthesis of current knowledge on contaminant concentrations, fate in the environment and risk assessment	Do contaminants compromise the use of recycled nutrients in organic agriculture? A review and synthesis of current knowledge on contaminant concentrations, fate in the environment and risk assessment - ScienceDirect	yes
Article	18S-NemaBase: Curated 18S rRNA Database of Nematode Sequences	18S-NemaBase: Curated 18S rRNA Database of Nematode Sequences	yes
Article	Study of microbial communities in Lusitanian organic and conventional agricultural soils by phospholipid fatty acid analysis	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Resumo_CICS2022_NEW.docx.pdf	No
Article	In defence of soil biodiversity: Towards an inclusive protection in the European Union	In defence of soil biodiversity: Towards an inclusive protection in the European Union	Yes
Article	The impact of crop diversification, tillage and fertilization type on soil total microbial, fungal and bacterial abundance: A worldwide meta-analysis of agricultural sites	The impact of crop diversification, tillage and fertilization type on soil total microbial, fungal and bacterial abundance: A worldwide meta-analysis of agricultural sites	Yes
Article	Development and effectivity of <i>Solanum sisymbriifolium</i> against potato cyst nematode under field conditions in soils from the southern atlantic area	Development and effectivity of <i>Solanum sisymbriifolium</i> against potato cyst nematode under field conditions in soils from the southern atlantic area	Yes
Article	Fostering Sustainable Potato Production: A Collaborative European Approach	Fostering Sustainable Potato Production: A Collaborative European Approach	Yes
Article	Wheat field earthworms under divergent farming systems across a European climate gradient	Wheat field earthworms under divergent farming systems across a European climate gradient	Yes
Article	Puccinia Spore Concentrations in Relation to Weather Factors and Phenological Development of a Wheat Crop in Northwestern Spain	Puccinia Spore Concentrations in Relation to Weather Factors and Phenological Development of a Wheat Crop in Northwestern Spain	Yes

PUBLICATIONS

Article	Aeromycological studies in the crops of the main cereals: A systematic review	Aeromycological studies in the crops of the main cereals: A systematic review	Yes
Article	Occurrence, persistence and risk assessment of pesticide residues in European wheat fields: A continental scale approach	Occurrence, persistence and risk assessment of pesticide residues in European wheat fields: A continental scale approach.	No
Article	Earthworm community structure under different land-use systems across various soil conditions	Earthworm community structure under different land-use systems across various soil conditions	No
Article	The effects of agricultural practices on earth worm communities in Estonia	The effects of agricultural practices on earthworm communities in Estonia	No

4.2.2 Datasets

[Three comprehensive datasets](#) have been developed and made publicly available. These datasets provide valuable information on **soil biodiversity, agricultural practices, and environmental variables**.

All datasets are accessible through the ["Toolbox Kit"](#) section of the SoildiverAgro website.

Table 5 Datasets

DATASETS			
Type	Title	Link	Zenodo
Dataset	Soil microbial, fungal and bacterial abundance impacted by crop diversification, tillage and fertilizer type	Soil microbial, fungal and bacterial abundance impacted by crop diversification, tillage and fertilizer type Zenodo	Yes
Dataset	General soil properties of wheat fields along 9 Pedoclimatic regions in Europe	General soil properties of wheat fields along 9 Pedoclimatic regions in Europe	Yes
Dataset	Pesticides in the soil of wheat fields along 9 Pedoclimatic regions in Europe	Pesticides in the soil of wheat fields along 9 Pedoclimatic regions in Europe	Yes

4.2.3 Books and booklet

A total of **five books and one booklet** have been developed to share the key findings of the SoildiverAgro project. The **Best Management Practice Guidelines**, the **White Paper on Recommendations for EU Policy Updates**, and the **Regional Communities and Case Studies Booklet** highlight the final outcomes of the project across different thematic areas, including soil biodiversity, sustainable farming practices, policy development, and regional implementation. These publications are presented below:

Table 6 Books

BOOKS			
Type	Title	Link	Zenodo
Book	Handbook of the protocols employed in wp3 for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis	Handbook-WP3-PROTOCOLS-FOR-SAMPLING-GENERAL-SOIL-CHARACTERIZATION-AND-SOIL-BIODIVERSITY-ANALYSIS.pdf (soildiveragro.eu)	Yes
Book	Protocols for sampling general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis	Handbook-WP5-Handbook-on-case-studies-set-up-protocols-for-sampling-sample-procedure-and-analysis.pdf (soildiveragro.eu)	Yes
Book	Interactions between agricultural management and soil biodiversity: an overview of current knowledge	E-book.-Interactions-between-agricultural-management-and-soil-biodiversity.-An-overview-of-current-knowledge.pdf (soildiveragro.eu)	Yes
Book	White Paper on Recommendations for EU Policies Updating	FINAL_27_SoildiverAgro_WHIT E-PAPER-ON-RECOMMENDATIONS.pdf	No
Book	Best Management Practices Guidelines	FINAL_27_SoildiverAgro_BEST-PRACTICE-GUIDELINES.pdf	No
Booklet	Regional Communities and case studies booklet	Regional Communities and case studies booklet.	Yes

White Paper on policy recommendations

A White Paper on policy recommendations for the European Union was developed within the SoildiverAgro project to support the enhancement of soil biodiversity in agricultural systems. This policy-oriented document synthesizes research findings and stakeholder input to promote sustainable land management and align proposed actions with existing EU and regional frameworks.

Through collaboration with farmers, scientists, and policymakers, the White Paper underscores the urgent need for targeted measures to protect soil biodiversity, emphasizing its importance for ecosystem health, agricultural resilience, and long-term food security. It also addresses current knowledge gaps, introduces practical indicators for on-farm application, and outlines a clear strategy for integrating soil biodiversity into agricultural policy and practice.

In addition, the White Paper presents concrete policy recommendations based on findings generated throughout SoildiverAgro project. It also identifies key barriers to the implementation of these measures.

The White Paper is publicly accessible through the [“Toolbox Kit”](#) section of the SoildiverAgro website.

Figure 57 White Paper on recommendations for EU policies

Best Management Practices Guidelines Manual

The Best Management Practices Guidelines Manual was developed to compile the best agricultural practices identified from case studies across Europe during the SoildiverAgro project. Focused on promoting soil biodiversity, it offers practical, innovative solutions for a wide range of agricultural problems, including soil health improvement, the reduction of inputs like fertilizers and pesticides or increase plant growth and development on farms.

Developed with input from farmers, researchers, and policymakers, the guidelines support both environmental and economic benefits, helping address real agricultural challenges while promoting soil fertility, reducing emissions, and improving resource efficiency.

The best practices selected from each case study and included in the manual are the following ones:

- Case study 1 . Use of soil biodiversity to reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence and increase nutrient availability in potatoes cropped in multiple cropping and rotations.
- Case study 2. Use of soil biodiversity to increase nutrient and water availability and reduce soil-borne diseases incidence to increase wheat yields.
- Case study 3. Use of crop diversification and trap crops in potato fields.
- Case study 4. Use of mycorrhizas in potato fields to reduce the incidence on the common scab, decrease the use of phosphorus fertilizers, increase crop yields and soil biodiversity.
- Case study 5. Exploring the implementation of the Decision Support Systems (DSS) to reduce the use of fungicides in potato and wheat crops and their impact on soil biodiversity.
- Case study 6. Soil management strategies to improve soil quality while minimizing external input of N and P in potato crops.
- Case study 7. Cover crop mixtures: a promoter of soil biodiversity in potato crops?
- Case study 8. Intensive versus extensive versus organic vegetable farming
- Case study 9. Improving agro-ecological crop production by application of different sources of green manure.
- Case study 10a. Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in conventional wheat cropping systems.
- Case study 10b. Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in organic potato cropping systems.
- Case study 11. Potential of plant diversity to promote intrinsic soil self-regulation processes and to enhance fungivorous soil fauna communities in wheat cropping systems.
- Case study 12. Impact of agricultural management and tillage practices on soil biota.
- Case study 13. Increase of soil biodiversity through amendment of forest based organic material in potato crops.
- Case study 14a and 14b. Contrasting continuous plant cover and minimum tillage with 117 inversion tillage in wheat fields.
- Case study 15. Use of catch crop in farmed potato fields.

This manual is publicly accessible through the [“Toolbox Kit”](#) section of the SoildiverAgro website. In addition, a number of printed copies have been distributed across the participating regions to ensure broader reach and practical use.

Figure 58 Best Management Practices Guidelines Manual

4.2.4 Posters

A total of [20 posters](#) were developed to visually communicate key aspects of the **SoildiverAgro** research. Several of these posters summarize individual **case studies**, highlighting their objectives, methodologies, results, and best practices. The collection also includes thematic posters covering special events.

Figure 59 Case study posters mockup

All posters are accessible through the "[Toolbox Kit](#)" section of the SoildiverAgro website.

Table 7 Posters

POSTERS	
Title	Link
Case study 1	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs1.pdf
Case study 2	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs2.pdf
Case study 3	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/poster-CS3.pdf
Case study 4	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-CS4.pdf
Case study 5	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-CS5_v2.pdf
Case study 6	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-CS6.pdf
Case study 7	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-CS7.pdf
Case study 8	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-CS8.pdf
Case study 9	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Poster-cs9.pdf
Case study 10a	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs10a_v2.pdf
Case study 10b	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs10b.pdf
Case study 11	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs11.pdf
Case study 12-1	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs12-1.pdf
Case study 12-2	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs12-2.pdf
Case study 13	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs13.pdf
Case study 14	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs14.pdf
Case study 15	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Poster-cs15.pdf
12 th International Symposium on Earthworm Ecology	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Briones-et-al_SoildiverAgro-poster.pdf
WCSS 2022 Glasgow	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/WCSS_Poster_EvaLloret.pdf
SoildiverAgro Case studie general poster	https://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/cartel-CS-web.pdf

4.2.5 Practice Abstract

The European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) requires the development of Practice Abstracts (PAs) as a fundamental component of EU-funded research and innovation projects, particularly those under the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe frameworks. These abstracts serve to bridge the gap between scientific research and practical application by delivering clear, concise, and actionable information to farmers, agricultural advisors, and other practitioners.

As part of its commitment, the SoildiverAgro project has produced 114 [Practice Abstracts](#). These abstracts address key topics such as enhancing soil biodiversity, reducing pesticide use, improving soil quality through the use of cover crops, and implementing sustainable farming techniques adapted to different regional climates. To ensure that this content is accessible and easily understood by farmers, a standardized template was created. This template enhances the visual presentation of the abstracts, making them more comprehensible, engaging, and user-friendly.

All Practice Abstracts are accessible through the ["Toolbox Kit"](#) section of the SoildiverAgro website and are available in both English and the respective local languages of the regions from which they originate.

Figure 59 Practice Abstract mockup

Figure 60 Practice Abstract webpage

4.2.6 Policy brief

[Policy briefs](#) were developed as a result of the case studies implemented within the SoildiverAgro project. A total of six regional policy briefs were produced, one for each pedoclimatic region (Lusitanian, Boreal, Nemoral, Atlantic Central, Continental and Mediterranean).

These concise documents highlight the key soil biodiversity challenges specific to each area, the sustainable agricultural practices applied, and the benefits observed. Each brief also presents the SoildiverAgro approach, which integrates scientific research with stakeholder collaboration to promote practical, regionally adapted solutions. The briefs are intended to support policymakers and practitioners in incorporating soil biodiversity into sustainable land management strategies tailored to local conditions.

The policy brief are publicly available on SoildiverAgro website in the ["Toolbox Kit"](#) section.

Figure 61 Policy brief of the Atlantic Central Region

4.2.7 Survey on soil biodiversity policies

A survey on soil biodiversity policies was conducted during the last stages of the project to collect feedback on the policy recommendations developed through the project and to better understand how the SoildiverAgro is perceived by its community and stakeholders.

It was created on the EU Survey platform, an online tool developed by the European Commission to collect feedback, data, and insights from stakeholders, citizens, and organizations across the European Union. The survey was divided in the following sections:

- **General information:** participants were asked to provide their professional and other detail to identify their profile.

- **Soil biodiversity policies:** respondents were inquired about their knowledge and perceptions regarding the impact of European soil biodiversity policies.
- **Perceptions on SoildiverAgro regional policy recommendations:** based on the results of case studies, several policy recommendations were tailored for each region. Participants were asked to indicate their region, and depending on their response, relevant policy recommendations were displayed. They were then asked about their perceptions of the potential impact of these policies in their region, including their effectiveness, feasibility, and any possible barriers to implementation.
- **Awareness and perception of SoildiverAgro:** this section aims to understand participants opinions and perceptions of the SoildiverAgro project and its impact.
- **Practical implementation and future collaboration:** respondents were asked whether they had applied any soil biodiversity-friendly practices and their willingness to collaborate in the future.

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

Stakeholder Survey on Soil Biodiversity Policies and the SoildiverAgro Project

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Disclaimer
The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

Views
Standard Accessibility Mode

Languages
English

Contact
Contact Form

Save as Draft

Report Abuse

Stakeholder Survey on Soil Biodiversity Policies and the SoildiverAgro Project

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey. Your input is invaluable in assessing the impact of soil biodiversity policies and understanding stakeholders' perceptions of the SoildiverAgro project. The survey will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete.

General Information

Figure 62 SoildiverAgro survey on soil biodiversity policies

Additionally, the survey was available in 6 different languages, corresponding to the ones spoken in the regions of the SoildiverAgro project:

- [English](#)
- [Spanish](#)
- [Dutch](#)
- [German](#)
- [Finnish](#)
- [Estonian](#)

To promote the survey, a [landing page](#) was launched at the SoildiverAgro website. Moreover, posts on social media were published and regional coordinators spread the survey among regional stakeholders.

Figure 63 Survey social media promotion banner

The survey will be maintained until the end of the SoildiverAgro project and results will be included at the technical report.

4.2.8 Decision Support Tool

A [Decision Support Tool \(DST\)](#) was developed during the project to help end-users, including farmers and other stakeholders, optimize their wheat cropping systems and management practices.

It consists of an user-friendly web-based software which uses machine learning models developed from experimental data collected during the SoildiverAgro project to predict agricultural soil properties. It considers the environmental, physicochemical, and land-use parameters, as well as biodiversity indices. The tool guides users through a step-by-step process, asking for key information such as pedoclimatic conditions, crop location, agricultural challenges, and current cropping systems. Based on this input, the DST provides tailored recommendations to enhance productivity, profitability, and sustainability.

Figure 64 DST Data upload section

Sample Code	Tillage system (choose from list)	Fertilization (choose from list)	Pesticides (choose from list)
soil1	1. Conventional tillage - deep soil inversion (ploughing till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically at 25 cm)	2. Organic	7. Combination
soil2	3. No tillage - no mixing, no inversion (direct seeding, subsoiler)	3. Mineral	2. H = Herbicides
soil3	3. No tillage - no mixing, no inversion (direct seeding, subsoiler)	4. Organic+mineral	6. B = Biocides

Figure 65 DST excel template

sample	tillage	fertilization	pesticides	PedoClim (choose from list)
soil1	1. Conventional tillage - deep soil inversion (ploughing till a depth of 15-35 cm, typically at 25 cm)	2. Organic	7. Combination	3. Boreal
soil2	3. No tillage - no mixing, no inversion (direct seeding, subsoiler)	3. Mineral	2. H = Herbicides	3. Boreal
soil3	3. No tillage - no mixing, no inversion (direct seeding, subsoiler)	4. Organic+mineral	6. B = Biocides	6. Mediterranean North
soil4	4. Reduced tillage - deep mixing without inversion (cultivator, spader, rotavader till a depth of 15-35 cm)	1. None	2. H = Herbicides	6. Mediterranean North

Figure 66 DST "Check upload" section – Metadata

Figure 67 DST “Check upload” section – Physicochemical

Figure 68 DST “Check upload” section – Climate

Figure 69 DST yield prediction

To support users on using the DST, a dedicated [landing page](#) was created on the SoildiverAgro website. This page offers a detailed, step-by-step guide that outlines the process in a clear and visually accessible manner. The three steps are as follows:

- **Step 1:** download the excel template, where users can input the parameters and data for their soil samples. Then, they will have to upload the excel file by using the “browse botton”
- **Step 2:** verify that the data has been correctly uploaded. Users can view the information in various tables, categorized by data type.
- **Step 3:** view the predictions provided by the DST based on the uploaded data section. Here, they will find predicions on yied, nematode biodiversity, fungal biodiversity and bacterial biodiversity. Additionally, numerical values at displayed at the bottom of the DST providing raw prediction, percentiles and percentiles per region values.

Figure 41 DST landing webpage

Figure 70 guidelines on the DST landing webpage

4.3 Events (in person and online)

A total of 121 events were organized by the SoildiverAgro project across its various regions since project launch, including training sessions, regional meetings, field days, and discussion groups. These events played a key role in engaging stakeholders, disseminating knowledge, and promoting sustainable practices developed throughout the project

Table 8 SoildiverAgro Events

	Discussion group	Field day	Other	Regional meeting	Training
Atlantic	4	19	9	5	5
Boreal	6	4	7	5	3
Continental	1	2	2	5	3
Lusitanian	3	4	1	2	3
Mediterranean	2	3	1	5	1
Nemoral	2	2	9	1	2
TOTAL	18	34	29	23	17

A more detailed account of each event organized across the different regions is available in the [Case Studies Booklet](#). This resource compiles all activities conducted by region and case study, including training sessions, regional stakeholder meetings, field demonstrations, and discussion groups. It serves as a comprehensive reference showcasing the regional engagement and knowledge-sharing efforts carried out during the project.

4.4 Participation in related events

SoildiverAgro partners also actively promoted the project's results at external events to broaden its reach and increase overall impact. These outreach efforts contributed to greater visibility, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of key outcomes. A detailed overview of these participations is provided in the following table, highlighting the events, locations, dates, and types of contributions made by project partners.

Table 9 Participation in related events

EVENT TITLE	PARTNER	DATE	LOCATION	ROLE
"The importance of soil microbiome in sustainable plant protection" Webinar	Luke	28/10/2021	Online	Oral presentation
RIES21	FEUGA	23-24/10/2021	Mondariz (Galicia)	Stand

EVENT TITLE	PARTNER	DATE	LOCATION	ROLE
Galicia Innovation Days	UVigo	29/10/2021	Online	Project presentation
EUGreenWeek	FEUGA	09/06/2021	Online	Project presentation
EIP AGRI Farm Data Seminar	EULS	09/12/2021	Online	Case study presentation
Konverents toimub üle veebi: liitu konverentsi ülekandega siit	EULS	03/12/2021	Online	Project presentation
FAO Global Symposium for soil Biodiversity	UVigo	19-22/04/2021	Online	Poster/ Video
HEALTHY SOILS FOR SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE	FEUGA	17/11/2021	Online	Attendance
Towards a FABulous CAP	EV-ILVO	11/06/2021	Online	Attendance
National Farmari exhibition	LUKE	30/06 – 2/07/2022	Mikkeli, Finland	Stand
International rural fair MAAMESS	MTUPK	21-23/04/2022	Tartu, Estonia	Stand
Festilvo	EV-ILVO	15-16-18-19/09/2022	Merelbeke, Belgium	Project presentation
Soil Health Conference	EV-ILVO	05/12/2022	Brussels, Belgium	Attendance
Network to Innovate: Crop Biodiversity	LUKE	18/04/2023	Online	Attendance
3 rd Global Soil Biodiversity Conference	UVigo	14/03/2023	Dublin, Ireland	Round table presentations
ASA, CSSA, SSSA International Annual Meeting	UPCT	29/10/2023 – 01/11/2023	Saint Louis, USA	Oral and poster presentation
Finnish Agricultural Science Days 2024	Luke	10-11/01/2024	Helsinki, Finland	Oral presentation
Network to Innovate: Soil Biodiversity Workshop	MTUPK	20/02/2024	Online	Oral presentation

EVENT TITLE	PARTNER	DATE	LOCATION	ROLE
European Mission Soil Week	UVigo	12-13/11/2024	Brussels, Belgium	Co-creation breakout session
Regenerative Agriculture Workshop	MTUPK	12/12/2023	Online	Oral presentation
MAAMESS Expo	MTUPK	18/04/2024	Tartu, Estonia	Attendance
Suelos Vivos	UVigo	05/12/2024	Galicia, Spain	Pannel discussion and stand
XII Soil Science Days 2025	Luke	6-7/01/2025	Helsinki, Finland	Oral presentation
XV Soil Day	MTUPK	05/12/2024	Estonia	Oral presentation
Information day	MTUPK	16/12/2024	Estonia	Oral presentation
Scientific Webinar Series	Luke	16/01/2025	Online	Oral presentation
Nothern Roots Forum	MTUPK and EULS	22-23/01/2025	Tallin, Estonia	Stand
2 nd Spanish National Conference on Organic Agriculture	UPCT	25-26/02/2025	Murcia, Spain	Oral communication panel
SOILGUARD Event: "From Soil Science to Policy" at the Forum for the Future of Agriculture	FEUGA	31/03/2025	Brussels, Belgium	Stand

5 KPIS evaluation

Table 10 SoildiverAgro KPIS

CHANNELS	DESCRIPTION	KPIS	REACHED
Website	A dedicated website designed and developed to communicate the project and disseminate its findings. The website link also the Decision Support Tool and a Tool Box Kit with all guidelines and tutorial videos for end-users.	5.000 visitors	22,21K
Social Media	Professional social media accounts for SoildiverAgro created (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Youtube)	At least 500 followers in each social network account created	TW: 1104 FB: 173 LK: 364 YT: 30
Communication materials	Communication materials designed during the project lifetime to be used by partners when necessary. These materials were centralised in a branding guideline document to guarantee an effective and consistent branding of the project; and updated regularly to be adapted to the different messages to be communicated.	Power Point and Word templates Project banner, flyers and set of posters Project infographics and 4 Project Video content	All templates done 15 infographics 52 videos
Digital & Media press work	Digital and physical campaigns (press, radio, TV, etc.) were set- up for the promotion of the SoildiverAgro activities and developments	5 newsletters Radio/ TV interviews Communication campaigns	142 news created at website 6 newsletters sent 4 communication campaigns
Partners existing communication channels	Access to partners existing communication channels such as their websites, social networks accounts and others. These channels were included within the Communication Plan	To reach an audience of more than 50.000 institutions.	All partners published information related to the project on their own channels

6 Project legacy

At the final meeting of the **SoildiverAgro** project, all partners engaged in a dedicated discussion on the project's legacy and the long-term sustainability of its results. Several key actions were agreed upon to ensure continued impact and visibility beyond the project's official end.

To preserve and promote the outcomes of SoildiverAgro, the consortium committed to the following legacy actions:

- **Website maintenance:** The project website will remain active and publicly accessible for at least five additional years, until **May 2030**, serving as a central hub for all materials and updates.
- **Practice Abstracts:** These will continue to be available as concise, practical outputs targeted at farmers, advisors, and stakeholders.
- **Scientific dissemination:** All pending scientific papers will be finalized and published between **2025 and 2027**, both in peer-reviewed journals and in popular science and agricultural magazines to reach a broad audience.
- **Communities of Practitioners:** These networks, created to foster stakeholder engagement, will remain active to ensure ongoing dialogue and knowledge exchange.

In addition, SoildiverAgro will actively promote and make accessible the **tools and materials developed** during the final phase of the project, including:

- **Innovative tools for soil biodiversity assessment**
- **Best Management Practice Guidelines**
- **White Paper with policy recommendations**
- **Decision Support Tools** for sustainable agricultural practices

To further amplify its legacy, the project has also initiated collaboration with other initiatives. As part of the final event, a dedicated session titled “**Project Legacy: Interaction with Soil Biodiversity Projects**” was held to foster knowledge exchange between SoildiverAgro and projects funded under the new European calls. This interaction aims to build continuity and integration within the broader research and innovation landscape on soil biodiversity.

The measures outlined above are designed to ensure that the knowledge, tools, and collaborations developed through SoildiverAgro will continue to benefit stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers well beyond the project's completion.